

6G ✦ REFERENCE

6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing

6G-REFERENCE envisions a future where urban areas are equipped with sustainable solutions that can cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

6G ✦ REFERENCE will

Develop integrated circuit and antenna component solutions, including dynamic frequency and spatial antenna filtering to enable efficient spectrum coexistence schemes.

Deploy practical hardware enablers in terms of complexity, cost and power consumption that could end up constituting a reference design for future 6G-distributed radios.

Our Challenges

Our Methodology

The project targets **practical integrated circuits (IC) and antenna systems for 6G applications**. 6G-REFERENCE will:

Explore radio system operation in the 10-15GHz range

Develop hardware concepts and show feasibility in CMOS

Use additive manufacturing for antenna arrays and nanotechnology for sensors

More about 6G ✦ REFERENCE

✦ **Innovation and research project** running for 3 years, until December 2026

✦ **Joint collaboration** of 10 research and industry partners **from 8 European countries**

✦ 6G-REFERENCE is a project part of the **Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU)**

Follow us!

@6G_Reference

@6G-REFERENCE

@6G-REFERENCE

6greference.eu

6G SNS

Scan me!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101139155. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.